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6TH INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH SEMINAR - “AUTONOMOUS LEARNING IN EDUCATION”

Listener: Pedro Augusto da Cruz

1st Lecture: “Analysis and Discussion of Results: how to prepare”

Speaker: Dra. Augustina Subeldia

REVIEW:

The importance and methods for carrying out an effective analysis and discussion of results in scientific research are addressed, regardless of positive or negative results, the author’s perception of their objectives. According to the speaker, “data analysis” is an individual and specific task, while “discussion” is a broader term that involves the interpretation and contextualization of the data obtained. For an efficient analysis, it is essential to verify the codes used and align the research objective with the most viable statistical method. The presentation should describe in detail the topics covered, the methodological standards used and discuss the results in comparison with other investigations, highlighting the relevance and impact of the study. It is important to compare the results obtained with other research, to validate and contextualize the findings.

To ensure that data interpretations are accurate and well-founded. The responsibility for explaining the perception of the results falls on the researcher, who must consider the implications of the findings as scientific articles, assessing the importance and impact on learning and the advancement of knowledge.

Likewise, it is necessary to revisit the works and avoid common errors, such as the wrong selection of data or incorrect interpretations, maintain strict control of variables, and ensure transparency in data manipulation. The need for continuous training of teams involved in the research is evident. Combating errors requires the use of appropriate tools and software, as well as ongoing training of professionals.

It is emphasized that, in cases of unpublished studies, it is recommended to follow a phased study, starting with an exploratory phase to interview people, collect information and identify relevant research topics. This process must be carried out meticulously, showing the research stages step by step to ensure the validity and reliability of the results obtained.

Finally, the lecture highlights the importance of presenting the results in a clear and objective manner, facilitating understanding and discussion by the scientific community. Describing the methods and discussions in detail allows other researchers to replicate the study or use it as a basis for new investigations. Prof. Subeldia emphasizes that the analysis and discussion of results are crucial steps in scientific research, as they allow not only the validation of the data obtained, but also the contribution to the advancement of knowledge in various areas of knowledge.

Ferramentas usadas:

Pesquisa quantitativa	Pesquisa qualitativa
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Excel• SPSS• R• SAS (Statistical Analysis System)• STATA• Python• Entre otros	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• NVivo• ALTAS.ti• Provalis Research Text Analytics Software• Quirkos• MAXQDA• Dedoose• Raven's Eye

Pesquisa quantitativa	Pesquisa qualitativa
<p>Análise descritiva e inferencial</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Estatísticas descritivas• Testando hipóteses	<p>Identificação de Temas e Padrões</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Agrupamento temático• Avaliação do tópico
<p>Interpretação</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Resultados descritivos• Resultados inferenciais	<p>Interpretação de Temas e Padrões</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Análise de conteúdo• Comparação e contraste
	<p>Preparação de Narrativas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Desenvolvimento narrativo• Interpretação reflexiva

Pesquisa quantitativa	Pesquisa qualitativa
<p>Gráficos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gráficos de barras, linhas e dispersão • Tabelas de resumo <p>Descrição dos resultados</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dados descritivos: médias, medianas, desvios padrão • Dados inferenciais: testes t, ANOVA, regressões 	<p>Narrativa Descritiva</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descrição detalhada • Citações textuais <p>Tabelas e Figuras</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tabelas de resumo • Mapas conceituais

Pesquisa quantitativa	Pesquisa qualitativa
<p>Análise descritiva e inferencial</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estatísticas descritivas • Testando hipóteses <p>Interpretação</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resultados descritivos • Resultados inferenciais 	<p>Identificação de Temas e Padrões</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrupamento temático • Avaliação do tópico <p>Interpretação de Temas e Padrões</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Análise de conteúdo • Comparação e contraste <p>Preparação de Narrativas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desenvolvimento narrativo